

Spatial Cluster Analysis and Autocorrelation Test in East Java

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Introduction

This document explains the steps for testing the spatial autocorrelation of economic variables in East Java, based on Dynamic Spatial Cluster, using several steps:

1. **Generating spatial weighted matrix of queen contiguity from the input map of East Java (shp file)**
 2. **Calculating the distance of two location's time series using Dynamic Time Warping (DTW)**
 3. **Generating the Minimum Spanning Tree (MST)**
 4. **Clustering using Skater Method**
 5. **Visualizing the clustering result map**
 6. **Generating panel version of spatial weighted matrix based on cluster result**
 7. **Generating panel version of spatial weighted matrix based on queen contiguity concept**
 8. **Testing Moran's I to detect spatial autocorrelation**
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1 Load Library

```
library(tidyverse)
library(tibble)
library(dplyr)
library(spdep)
library(rgdal)
library(bigDM)
library(sf)
library(lwgeom)
library(ggplot2)
library(RColorBrewer)
library(viridisLite)
library(ggsci)
library(gt)
sf_use_s2(FALSE)
```

Reading the East Java Map and Generating Spatial Weighted Matrix

```
# Load East Java map data
jatim.shp <- readOGR("C:/Users/Rahma Fitriani/Google Drive/Hibah Internal UB/
R Spatial Skater/Data/JatimData.shp")

## OGR data source with driver: ESRI Shapefile
## Source: "C:\Users\Rahma Fitriani\Google Drive\Hibah Internal UB\R Spatial
Skater\Data\JatimData.shp", layer: "JatimData"
## with 38 features
## It has 12 fields
## Integer64 fields read as strings:  SELECTED

summary(jatim.shp)

## Object of class SpatialPolygonsDataFrame
## Coordinates:
##      min      max
## x 110.89872 116.270189
## y  -8.78036  -5.048857
## Is projected: FALSE
## proj4string : [+proj=longlat +datum=WGS84 +no_defs]
## Data attributes:
##      PROVNO      KABKOTNO      PROVINSI      KABKOT
## Length:38      Length:38      Length:38      Length:38
## Class :character Class :character Class :character Class :character
## Mode  :character Mode  :character Mode  :character Mode  :character
##
##
##      X      Y      Y_1      X_1
## Min.   :111.2  Min.   :-8.349  Min.    :257.2  Min.    : 13235
## 1st Qu.:111.9  1st Qu.: -7.973  1st Qu.:282.5  1st Qu.: 19328
## Median :112.5  Median : -7.702  Median :310.8  Median : 24164
## Mean   :112.6  Mean   : -7.649  Mean   :333.2  Mean   : 40231
## 3rd Qu.:113.1  3rd Qu.: -7.440  3rd Qu.:384.8  3rd Qu.: 40300
## Max.   :114.7  Max.   : -6.559  Max.   :511.3  Max.   :315401
##      Jenis      X_meter      Y_meter      SELECTED
## Min.   :1.000  Min.   :1181050  Min.   :9064917  Length:38
## 1st Qu.:1.000  1st Qu.:1264367  1st Qu.:9110284  Class :character
## Median :1.000  Median :1330831  Median :9140892  Mode  :character
## Mean   :1.237  Mean   :1335702  Mean   :9147019
## 3rd Qu.:1.000  3rd Qu.:1393941  3rd Qu.:9172010
## Max.   :2.000  Max.   :1572901  Max.   :9265403

# Regional Identity
ID <- "KABKOTNO"

# Queen Contiguity
queen <- poly2nb(jatim.shp, queen = TRUE)
```

```

peta.mod <- connect_subgraphs(jatim.shp, ID.area = ID, nb = queen, plot = TRUE)

## Searching for isolated areas:
## 0 region(s) with no links
##
## Searching for disjoint connected subgraphs:
## 2 disjoint connected subgraphs

```



```

# Check whether all regions are connected
n.comp.nb(peta.mod$nb)$nc == 1

## [1] TRUE

# Save the Queen Contiguity spatial weight matrix
peta.nb.2 <- peta.mod$nb
mat.queen <- nb2mat(peta.nb.2, style = "B")

```

Reading data for several economic variables as the basis of cluster analysis

```

datadtw <- read.csv("C:/Users/Rahma Fitriani/Google Drive/Hibah Internal UB/R
Spatial Skater/Data/data kompetitif GDP.csv", sep = ",")
da_f <- data.frame(datadtw)
da_t <- as_tibble(da_f)
name <- c("ID", "year", "GGDP", "GDP", "HDI", "Dens", "SWP")
names(da_t) <- name

```

Calculating DTW distance

See the documentation of `d_tw` function for a detailed explanation of this function.

```
source("f_dtw.R") # file name where the `dtw` function is stored
m_cost <- dtw(da_t, name)
```

Generating the Minimum Spanning Tree between locations based on distance/cost from the DTW concept

See the documentation of `m_st` function for a detailed explanation of this function.

```
source("f_m_st.R") # file name where the `m_st` function is stored
mst <- m_st(mat.queen, m_cost)[,1:2]
```

Generating the first Principal Component from economic variables

Each location has one PC in each year. See the documentation of `pc_data` function for a detailed explanation of this function.

```
source("f_pc_data.R") # file name where the `pc_data` function is stored
m_pc <- pc_data(da_t, name)
```

Spatial Cluster Analysis using the Skater Method

- 10 clusters will be formed based on the PC and MST data that have been obtained.
- See the documentation of `clust` function for a detailed explanation of this function.

```
source("f_clust.R") # file name where the `clust` function is stored
id_clus <- clust(mst, m_pc, 9)
```

Visualizing the clustering result map

```
n <- length(id_clus)
jatim_idclus <- as.data.frame(cbind(seq(1:n), as.character(id_clus)))
names(jatim_idclus) <- c("KABKOTNO", "Cluster")

write.csv(jatim_idclus, file = "C:/Users/Rahma Fitriani/Google Drive/Hibah Internal UB/R Spatial Skater/Data/Hasil Cluster.csv", row.names = FALSE)

# Load the East Java map with clustering results
jatim <- st_read("C:/Users/Rahma Fitriani/Google Drive/Hibah Internal UB/R Spatial Skater/Data/JatimData.shp")

## Reading layer `JatimData' from data source
## `C:\Users\Rahma Fitriani\Google Drive\Hibah Internal UB\R Spatial Skater\Data\JatimData.shp'
## using driver `ESRI Shapefile'
## Simple feature collection with 38 features and 12 fields
## Geometry type: MULTIPOLYGON
## Dimension: XY
## Bounding box: xmin: 110.8987 ymin: -8.78036 xmax: 116.2702 ymax: -5.04885
```


See the documentation of `w_kont` function for a detailed explanation of this function.

```
source("f_w_kont.R") # file name where the `w_kont` function is stored
wkont <- w_kont(mat.queen, 4)
std_baris_matq <- mat2listw(as.matrix(wkont), style = "W", zero.policy = TRUE
)
```

Detecting spatial autocorrelation using Moran's I

```
# Variable selection for Moran's Test
my_data <- da_t %>% dplyr::select(-!!sym(name[1]), -!!sym(name[2]), -!!sym(name[7]))

# Ensure data is only numeric
if (!all(sapply(my_data, is.numeric))) {
  stop("Data mengandung elemen non-numerik.")
}
my_data <- as.matrix(my_data)

# Moran's test with W Cluster
moran_results <- sapply(1:ncol(my_data), function(col) {
  moran.test(my_data[,col], std_baris_mat, alternative = "greater")$p.value
})
moran_df <- as.data.frame(t(moran_results))
colnames(moran_df) <- c("GGDP", "GDP", "HDI", "Dens")

# Moran's test with W Queen
moran_results_q <- sapply(1:ncol(my_data), function(col) {
  moran.test(my_data[,col], std_baris_matq, alternative = "greater")$p.value
})
moran_dfq <- as.data.frame(t(moran_results_q))
colnames(moran_dfq) <- c("GGDP", "GDP", "HDI", "Dens")

# Display the Moran's test results table
```

Moran's test p-value based on Dynamic Cluster-based Weighting

```
moran_df %>% gt()
```

GGDP	GDP	HDI	Dens
1.174474e-36	0.005620151	1.472928e-21	3.071118e-07

Moran's Test p-value based on Queen Contiguity Weighting

```
moran_dfq %>% gt()
```

GGDP	GDP	HDI	Dens
5.091623e-26	0.2963879	2.140603e-07	0.3343207